

Original Research Article

Effects of Increasing Concentrations of Some Kitchen Waste Peel Meals on Performance of Shaver Brown Birds

Oko E.C², Ahaotu E.O¹ and Mbachu M.U³

Abstract

A study was conducted to compare yam, sweet potato, Irish potato, plantain and banana peel meals (SKWPM) as sources of energy in layer chickens' diets. A total of 36 point of lay Shaver Brown birds were used for the study. Four treatments comprising of diets containing 0, 5, 10 and 20% levels of SKWPM were used in the study. The experiments lasted for 4 weeks. Result of the experiment showed that the control, 10 and 20% SKWPM diets produced similar final body weight, weight gain, feed intake, hen-day egg production and cumulative egg production per bird which were significantly better ($p < 0.05$) than those produced by 5% SKWPM diet. Ages at 1st egg and at 5% production were least ($p < 0.05$) for the control birds while the age at 50% production was least for the 10% SKWPM diets. From the result, it is inferred that layers should not be fed with diets containing more than 20% SKWPM.

Keywords: Some Kitchen Waste Peel Meals, Egg Production, Weight Gain, Feed Intake.

¹Department of Agricultural Technology,
Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic,
Unwana, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

²Department of Animal Production and
Health Technology, Imo State
Polytechnic, Omuma, Nigeria.

³Department of Agricultural Science,
Alvan Ikoku Federal College of
Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
emmaocy@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Availability of animal feed is one of the greatest constraints to the expansion of the livestock industry in developing countries (Nnadi *et al.*, 2021). Apart from the high and fluctuating costs, some of the ingredients used in mixed feeds, notably cereal grains, are in high demand for human consumption (Oko *et al.*, 2021). In view of the dwindling supply of the conventional feed resources and the shortage of foreign exchange for importation, alternative sources produced locally are being investigated.

The yam, sweet potato, Irish potato, plantain and banana plants, made up of the roots, leaves and stem, are good sources of carbohydrate and protein. The different parts of the plants can be used as animal feed. The leaves can be used as silage, dried for feed supplementation and as leaf meal for feed concentrates. The stem can be mixed with leaves and used as ruminant feed, or dried for feed concentrates. The roots can be chipped or pelletized and used as feed, while the root

peel, broken roots, fiber and baggase from starch extraction can be dried and used directly as animal feed or as substrate for single cell protein production. The use of sweet potato, Irish potato, plantain and banana roots as animal feed is increasing in importance in the developing countries where an export market for these commodities has developed (Atapattu and Senevirathne, 2012).

Sweet potato meal can be successfully used as a substitute for maize in broiler diets, but in most cases the highest substitution levels decrease performance (Edache *et al.*, 2012). The recommended inclusion level is usually 20%. Sweet potato has been used in layer diets, but a general trend of decreasing performance has been reported by (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2020). Safe inclusion rates should be limited to between 10 and 15% sweet potato meal in the diet, with proper protein and vitamin A supplementation (Iwuanyanwu *et al.*, 2019). Replacing 50% of maize with a mixture of sweet potato meal (21%

Table 1. Proximate Analysis of Some Kitchen Peel Waste Meal (Sweet Potato, Irish Potato, Unripe Plantain Peel, Ripe Banana Peel and Yam Peel)

Particular	Value
Ash	5.57%
Ether Extract	3.78%
Crude Fiber	4.25%
Carbohydrate	17.1%
Crude protein	6.88%
Moisture	7%
Elemental analysis	%
Calcium	0.34
Phosphorus	0.49
Iron	0.006
Potassium	0.41
Sodium	0.03
Essential amino acid	%
Lysine	0.07
Methionine	0.03
Vitamin analysis	%
Thiamine	0.009
Riboflavin	0.004
Niacin	0.015
Ascorbic acid	0.016

Table 2. Composition of the Experimental Diets (Point of Lay)

Ingredients	Treatments			
	T ₁ 0	T ₂ 5	T ₃ 10	T ₄ 20
Maize	40.0	40.0	40.0	40.0
Wheat Offal	20.00	15.00	10.00	0.00
Some Kitchen Waste Peel Meal (Sweet Potato, Irish Potato, Unripe Plantain Peel, Ripe Banana Peel and Yam Peel)	0.00	5.00	10.00	20.00
Palm Kernel Meal	7.10	7.10	7.10	7.10
Fish Meal	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
Soya bean Meal	16.5	16.5	16.5	16.5
Bone Meal	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5
Lysine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Methionine	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15
Common Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Layers Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Total (Kg)	100	100	100	100
Crude Protein (%)	17.9	18.3	18.2	17.9
Crude Fiber (%)	2.45	2.47	3.01	3.70
Ether Extract (%)	4.00	4.50	5.00	5.45
Ash Content (%)	11.0	12.0	12.0	12.50
Moisture Content (%)	13.00	13.00	12.50	13.00
ME (Kcal/Kg)	2665.0	2676.2	2677.9	2647.3
Calcium	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.6
Phosphorus	0.7	0.9	0.7	0.7

Layer Vitamin/mineral premix containing the following per kg. Vitamin A 10,000000IU; Vitamin D₃ 2,000000IU; Vitamin E 10,000IU; Vitamin K 2,000mg; Thiamine 1,500mg; Riboflavin B 4,000mg; Pyridoxine B₆ 1,500mg; Antioxidant 125g; Niacin 15,000mg; Vitamin B₁₂, 10mg; Pantothenic acids 5,000mg; Biotin 50mg; Choline chloride 400g, manganese 80g; Zinc, 20g; Iron, 50g; copper, 20g; Iodine 1.5g; Selenium 200mg; Cobalt 200mg; Folic acid 500mg; Vitamin C 100mg.

of the diet), wheat bran and sweet potato leaf meal was found to be acceptable though it significantly reduced egg

production by 5.6% (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2012 and 2013).

Dried plantain leaves replacing 10% of a standard

conventional diet in broilers did not affect feed efficiency or feed conversion (Yitbarek *et al.*, 2019). Maximum inclusion rates of 7.5% and 10% dried banana peels have been suggested for broiler diets. Live-weight gain and feed conversion efficiency were significantly higher in chickens fed up to 10% banana peel meal in the diet. Feed intake increased linearly as the level of peels increased to 10%, after which growth decreased (Ahaotu *et al.*, 2017). Table 1,2 above

Broiler chick growth was not compromised when yam peel meal was included at 150g/kg diet. Ayodele (2011) observed that yam peel meal at 250g/kg diet was optimum for broiler growth and carcass traits. Diarra *et al.* (2012) recommended a yam-sweet potato peel mixture (1:1 weight per weight) at 68 and 224 g/kg diet for starter and finisher broilers, respectively. It was concluded that a yam-sweet potato peel mixture can replace maize up to 15 and 45% in broiler starter and finisher diets, respectively, without adverse effects on the growth, haematological profile and carcass measurements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

This study was conducted at the Poultry Section of Department of Animal Production and Health Technology Teaching and Research Farm, Imo State Polytechnic Umuagwo. Umuagwo is located in Ohaji Egbema Local Government Area of Imo State. The site lies on latitude 5°18'49.65"N and Longitude 6°52'40.77"E with an altitude of 1293. It has an area of 890 km² and a population of 182,538 at the 2006 census. The local council lies in the south-western part of Imo State. It shares common boundaries with Owerri in the East, Oguta LGA in the North and Ogba/ Egbema/ Ndoni in Rivers State in the South-west (Egele, 2015).

Processing Some Kitchen Waste Peel Meal (Sweet Potato, Irish Potato, Unripe Plantain Peel, Ripe Banana Peel and Yam Peel)

Sweet Potato, Irish Potato, Unripe Plantain, Ripe Banana and Yam peels were collected fresh from Kitchens and restaurants in Umuagwo town. The peels were dehydrated by sun drying for 7 days to reduce enzymatic and microbial reactions that can lead to spoilage and nutrient leaching. The sun drying was also aimed at enhancing crispness and to reduce anti-nutritional factors that may be present in the yam peels. The dried peels were then milled in a hammer mill to form some kitchen waste peel meal.

Chemical Analysis of Sweet Potato, Irish Potato, Unripe Plantain Peel, Ripe Banana Peel and Yam Peel.

Samples of SKWPM were collected and analysed for proximate analysis according to (AOAC, 2000) at Federal Institute of Industrial Research Oshodi (FIIRO), Lagos state, Nigeria. Table 1 shows the proximate composition of SKWPM.

Feed formulation and plan of experiment

SKWPM was included at 0, 5, 10 and 20% level of inclusions to form 4 dietary treatments designated T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively in a completely randomized design. The inclusion of the SKWPM indicated that T₁ 0% SKWPM is the control diet. T₂ contained 5% SKWPM, T₃ contained 10% SKWPM and T₄ contained 20% SKWPM as shown in Table 2. At the beginning of the studies, the laying birds were assigned on equal weight bases to the dietary treatments. Three birds were randomly assigned to the 4 dietary treatments. A three-day adaptation period was allowed for the birds to acclimatize with the pens and feed, followed by quantitative collection of total droppings at 24 hourly intervals. Close monitoring was given to check spillage of feed from the troughs. The daily feed fed to each group was weighed daily in the morning to determine feed intake during the trial. The droppings for each of the 3-day collection period per group were rid - off extraneous materials weighed fresh, oven dried at 105°C for 72hours to content weigh before they were bulked and finely ground to obtained homogenous sample.

Experimental Animals and management

A total of thirty-six (36) shaver brown laying birds were purchased from a commercial farm were used for the experiment. They were randomly allotted to four dietary treatments of three replicate each with three (3) birds per replicate. The birds were housed in pens measuring (width 35cm width x 40cm length x 45cm height). The experimental diets and clean drinking water were provided *ad-libitum* throughout the experimental period of four (4) weeks.

Egg Production Performance and Quality

Egg production was recorded daily and feed consumption was recorded weekly throughout the experiment. Eggs from each group were collected bi-weekly to measure egg weight.

Table 3. Egg production performance of laying hen for a period of 4 weeks

Parameter	SKWPM content (%)				Level of significance
	0	5	10	20	
Feed consumption (g/b/d)	105.14	105.42	104.95	105.07	0.58 ^{ns}
Egg mass production (g/h/d)	48.10	46.57	43.31	46.08	0.55 ^{ns}
Feed conversion ratio	2.19	2.27	2.45	2.28	0.54 ^{ns}
Feed cost (N/kg egg) produced	33.46	33.10	32.84	32.46	<0.0001**
Feed cost (hen/d)	3.52	3.49	3.45	3.41	<0.0001**
Egg production (%)	57.07	53.81	51.99	52.90	0.45 ^{ns}
Egg weight (g/egg)	40.14	39.29	40.06	39.02	0.81 ^{ns}
Survivability (%)	100	100	100	100	0.00 ^{ns}
Egg breaking strength	1500.90	1504.77	1500.95	1506.01	0.11 ^{ns}

Ns: not-significant, g gram, b bird, d day, h hen

** P < 0.01, significant at 1% level

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the proximate composition of SKWPM and nutrient composition of experimental diets are presented on Table 1. The SKWPM had crude protein value of 6.88%, crude fiber 4.25% Ash 5.57% and metabolisable energy (ME) of 2280 kcal/kg. The values reported here were similar (Uchewa *et al.*, 2014). Calcium, moisture, ash values of 0.60 to 2.72, 9.06 to 12.83, and 9.06 to 12.83% were lower than those reported (Panda *et al.*, 2014). The egg production performance of laying hen for a period of 4 weeks is shown in Table 3 above.

Discussion

Inclusion of SKWPM slightly reduced the feed cost, although egg production and quality were statistically insignificant and found to be similar among the treatment groups. A slightly higher egg production and better feed conversion ratio were observed in the control group, which might be due to the high feed intake of hens compared to the SKWPM fed hens. Again, this lower egg production may be due to the fibre content in SKWPM arising from the poor nutrient utilization by birds.

However, the results are in agreement with some of the studies with sweet potato used as a substitute for maize. Odoemelam *et al.* (2020) and Sultana *et al.*, (2011) suggested that sun-dried sweet potato meal at a substitution rate of 50% can safely be added in the diets of laying hens without any negative effect on egg production.

In contrast, Mozafari *et al.* (2013) did not observe any significant difference in the cumulative egg production when sweet potato was incorporated up to 20% in the diets of laying hens. Afolayan *et al.* (2013) also reported that 20% replacement of wheat offal in the diets of laying hens with sweet potato meal led to no significant differences in the feed costs per kg of egg production and laying performances.

CONCLUSION

The results in this study suggested that there were no significant differences in egg production, egg mass production and feed consumption among the treatment groups with up to 20% inclusion rates of SKWPM. Furthermore, no significant difference was observed on either egg weight or survivability of laying hens fed on SKWPM diets. These results suggested that SKWPM could be safely included up to 20% in laying hens, without causing any negative effects on the production performance. However, we were able to reduce the production cost by up to 4%.

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